

Aspect sentiment distribution and change in multiple rounds of peer review comments

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Introduction

Peer review comments (PRC) for academic articles contain a variety of sentiments from referees. Journal articles generally need to be revised by several rounds of review, and reviewers' sentiments may change in different rounds. By mining the aspect sentiment in PRC, we can better understand the reviewers' attitude toward aspects, which can provide direction for submitters to optimize articles.

Some scholars investigated the PRC using sentiment analysis techniques. Chakraborty et al. (2020) adopted the reviewing aspects used in ACL conference and conducted sentiment analysis on the PRC of ICLR conference. They found that the distribution of aspect-based sentiments differed between accepted and rejected articles. However, these aspects pertain to overall evaluation of the articles. And they did not distinguish review round, which can help find the sentiment change of aspects concerned by reviewers. Therefore, this paper explores the distribution and change of aspect sentiment in multiple rounds of PRC at fine-grained aspect level. We construct a corpus of PRC annotated with aspect sentiment by PRC of *Nature Communications*¹ (NC). We use classification model to predict the aspect sentiment in all unannotated corpus. Finally, we analyze the aspect sentiment distribution and change of PRC in different rounds.

Method

The framework of this paper is shown in figure 1. It mainly includes sentiment annotation of reviews aspect and classification model of aspect sentiment.

Figure 1. The framework of this study

Sentiment annotation of reviews aspect

Annotation data are obtained from the multiple rounds of PRC corpus constructed by Han et al. (2022) based on the PRC of NC. Han et al. (2022) used double propagation algorithm to extract fine-

grained review aspects. They identified 11 aspect clusters through affinity propagation algorithm, including *Impact & Research Value*, *Methodology & Model*, etc. Based on this study, we use Stanford-core NLPⁱⁱ tool to syntactically parse sentences of PRC. Then, we extract the sentences containing the evaluation of the aspects in the above aspect clusters.

Three annotators label aspect sentiment in the review sentences regarding the annotation framework. The sentiment labels include positive, negative and neutral. We divide the corpus into three parts. For each part, two annotators independently label the sentiment. Kappa coefficient is used to calculate the annotation consistency between every two annotators, and the values are 0.62, 0.68, and 0.62. For the data with inconsistent labels, the third annotator finally checks the annotation. In total, We annotate 1,498 positive, 1,652 neutral and 1,913 negative aspect sentiment sentences respectively.

Classification model of aspect sentiment

We mainly use deep learning models to understand the relationship between aspects and context. This paper employs the LCF-BERT model proposed by Zeng et al. (2019), which is based on the idea that words closer to the aspect have a greater influence on the final sentiment inclination of the aspect. The model uses the local context focus and the semantic relative distance (SeRD) to determine whether the words are the local context of a specific aspect. Based on SeRD, the Context dynamic mask (CDM) and Context features Dynamic Weighted (CDW) are calculated. The model focuses more on the local context of aspects and locates sentiment information corresponding to the aspect more accurately.

Results Analysis

Comparison of model training results

The annotation data set is divided into training and test sets in an 80/20 ratio. The aspect sentiment classification models are trained in the annotation data. The evaluation results of the models are shown in Table 1.

The results show that BERT-based model outperforms other deep learning-based models in the aspect sentiment classification task. LCF-BERT model using CDM method has the best performance. It improves the accuracy by weakening relatively few semantically available features and focusing

more on local context words of specific aspects. Therefore, we finally use LCF-BERT model to predict the aspect sentiment of all 41,373 PRC.

Table 1. Experiment results of deep learning models

Model	Accuracy (%)	Macro-P(%)	Macro-R(%)	Macro-F1(%)
AOA	68.61	68.60	69.04	68.77
CABASC	68.71	69.57	68.07	68.31
IAN	69.60	70.08	69.53	69.47
ATAE_LSTM	69.79	71.00	69.48	69.76
MEMNET	71.37	72.80	70.89	71.15
AEN_BERT	76.41	77.54	76.17	76.40
BERT_SPC	81.05	81.99	80.76	80.85
LCF_BERT_CDW	81.15	82.32	80.77	81.02
LCF_BERT_CDM	82.72	83.43	82.45	82.65

Sentiment distribution in multiple rounds of reviews

We first compute the frequency of positive, negative and neutral sentiments for each aspect in all reviews. Then, we sum the sentiment frequency of each aspect in the same category according to the aspect clusters identified by Han et al. (2022). The statistical results are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Sentiment frequency of aspects

We make the same statistics for sentiment distribution in different rounds. Results show significantly more negative and neutral sentiments in every round compared to positive ones. It is due to peer review often evaluating manuscripts' academic quality critically and declaratively. In each round, the aspect clusters—*Result Analysis & Evaluation*, *Impact & Research Value*, *Methodology & Model* involve relatively more sentiments. The aspect words—*Data*, *Figure*, *Result*, *Analysis* involve the most sentiments. It indicates that these aspects have continuously received more attention and evaluation from reviewers. Therefore, it advises submitters to pay more attention to these aspects in writing papers.

Change of aspect sentiment in multiple rounds

To explore the change of aspect sentiment distribution in different rounds, we calculate proportion of the sentiment polarity frequency in all sentiments from each aspect cluster. As shown in

Figure 3(a) and (b), when the total review round is two or three, with the number of review rounds increasing, each aspect shows that the proportion of positive sentiments increases. After articles are revised according to PRC, the sentiment tendency of reviewers gradually shifts towards the positive. However, the overall change magnitude of each aspect's positive sentiment distribution is small. That is, the aspect sentiments in different review rounds do not change significantly compared to the first round. It indicates that submitters should ensure the quality of manuscripts when submitting.

Figure 3. Change of positive sentiment ratio

Conclusion

This paper constructs an aspect sentiment data set of peer review with multiple rounds to explore the distribution and change of aspect sentiment. The results show that the negative and neutral sentiments of reviews are in the majority. With the increase of rounds, the proportion of positive sentiments of each aspect increases, but the overall magnitude of change is small. This study can guide submitters to focus on aspects such as *Result Analysis & Evaluation* and *Impact & Research Value*, which receive more evaluation from reviewers in every round.

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ⁱ <https://www.nature.com/ncomms/>

ⁱⁱ <http://nlp.stanford.edu/software/tagger.shtml>